

Relationship Between Emotional Intelligence and Motivation for Occupational Preference Among Junior Secondary School Students in Birnin Kebbi Educational Zone, Kebbi State

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Abstract

The main purpose of the study was to find out the relationship between emotional intelligence and motivation for occupational preference among Junior Secondary School Students in Birnin Kebbi educational zone. Five research objectives were raised to guide the study. The research questions and research hypothesis are in line with stated objectives, a descriptive survey research method was used. The population of the study and the sample size were four thousand one hundred and fifty students (4150) and three hundred and fifty respondents (350) respectively by using the Research Advisor Table (2006). Two adopted questionnaires developed by Daniel Goleman (EIQ) and that of Bakare (MOPS) were administered. Inferential statistics were used to answer all the research questions using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. The findings of the research were positive among Junior Secondary School Students in Birnin Kebbi Educational zone. The study recommended that vocational guidance and counselling services should be provided to all Secondary Schools in Kebbi State. Government and stakeholders should also give more emphasis on vocational courses. To be run in schools. In conclusion, the study finally suggested that youths of Kebbi State should vocationally be oriented through clubs, associations, organizations and other social gatherings.

Keywords: Emotional intelligence, motivation, occupational preference, junior secondary school, students, educational zone.

Introduction

Youth in Kebbi State confront numerous challenges in terms of employment options. The majority of our students are relying on government service, which is extremely difficult to obtain due to population growth. As a result, young people are liabilities. While some rely on their parents, relatives, affluent people, and politicians, which makes them become neighborhood boys and neighborhood girls, others become lazy, which may push them to rob other people of their assets. Due to these factors, it is necessary to mentor and counsel our kids beginning in adolescence in order to provide them with the necessary abilities to be independent after graduation, even without a government employment. Youths are also valuable assets to their communities; however, they are often left out of decision making and occupational opportunities and go unheard. To build up stronger communities and more resilient youths, proper guidance and counselling services should be adequately provided for them since at the adolescent stage in order to develop up good and valuable citizens.

The main focus for many school leaders today is to provide students with high level of occupational opportunities. Every organization needs skillful students who will highly be involved in occupational participation in order to survive in today's complex business environment. (Brown, 2016). Emotional intelligence within the workplace could be related to student's involvement in an organisation. It is expected that students with higher emotional intelligence should have

higher level of occupational opportunities. In today's highly competitive business environment, Companies need their employees to be highly involved and dedicated with their jobs. (Khan, 2015).

Literature review

Emotional intelligence is extremely indispensable in functioning leadership positions as leaders wish everybody to fulfill his/her responsibilities and obligations as brilliantly as would be prudent. Research reveals that emotional intelligence has significant influences on the leadership roles and success of employment, and it is the prime variable for a successful life that contributes to better individuals' performance (Zijlmans et al., 2011 and Chastukhina, 2012). The leaders with an outstanding level of emotional intelligence apply their social capacities to move others, ensure durable relations with workers, and act as influential motivators by managing their emotions and perceiving their inadequacies. Leaders with an outstanding degree of emotional intelligence may be increasingly able to achieve more productivity from less manpower. Emotionally intelligent leaders can unexpectedly make and promote emotionally intelligent teams due to social many-sided nature of the present-day organizations (Goleman, 2002).

Motivation for occupational preference is based on individual work values (Macnab, et al.2005). Values are different from attitudes that can be positive or negative, whereas values are always positive in favor of something. This concept of values has frequently been used in the domain of work in connection with vocational choice and refers to a person's preference or liking for particular types of occupational activities (Roe & Ester 1999) Values are motivational constructs that guide the selection or evaluation of people's actions. Desirable abstract goals that people strive to attain (Schwartz, 2006) cited in Roe and Ester gave an elaborated definition of values as "desirable states, objects, goals, or behaviour, transcending specific situations and applied as normative standards to judge and to choose among alternative modes of behaviour. Values give direction to some of the most important decisions of life including the choice of academic discipline for making a career (Schwartz, 2006 in Berring, Kumari & Ahuja, 2015).

Occupational choices could be viewed then as preferences for settings that allow or encourage expression of particular values or value systems (Judge & Bretz, 2013). This is possible because individuals attach varying degrees of importance to different values and because work values have hierarchical features that can be ordered by their relative importance, they form an ordered system of value priorities that set individuals and groups apart making preferences and choices possible. For these reasons, a higher importance of one particular work value dimension implies a lower importance of another (Hauff & Kirchner, 2015). However, some researchers have argued that it is possible for values to be equal in intensity and thus equally high or equally low, he added therefore instead of a hierarchy particular relationships may exist between different work values, forming a specific value pattern, value system or value types (Roe and Ester, 2003).Most occupations involve some level of interaction with people however, an individual's personal values strongly impact both the type and quality of interaction that they will prefer to have with others while working (Macnab, et al.2005).

There are various categorizations of work values and among the various types there is a relative consensus on two central dimensions of work values (Kyvik, Yingying & Romero-Martinez, 2012; Lyons, Higgins & Duxbury, 2010; Sagie, Elizur, Koslowsky & Meni, 1996 in Hauff & Kirchner, 2015).These are extrinsic values (respectively security, material or instrumental values) which refer to aspects such as job security or income and Intrinsic values (respectively self-actualization or cognitive work values)which relate to aspects such as the pursuit of autonomy or having an interesting job. Beside these two basic dimensions, there have been suggestions for additional dimensions of work values: Social or relational values which refers to relations with co-workers, supervisors etc.; altruistic values which involve the desire to help others or to have a job that is useful to society and prestige values which are related to status, influence and power (Elizur et al., 1991; Gahan & Abeysekera, 2009; Lyons, Higgins and Duxbury, 2010; Ros, Schwartz & Surkiss, 1999 in Hauff & Kirchner, 2015).

Statement of the Problem

The researcher realized that most of the youths do not adequately understand their abilities, interest, values and do not generally relate their personal characteristics to the requirement of their preferred occupation, this problem lead to poor career choice, improper relationship with customers, job dissatisfaction and boredom creation with a given occupation. These and many other problems are factors that draw the attention of the researcher to investigate ways of relating the emotional intelligence with motivation for occupational preference.

Many times, it has been observed by the researcher that students chose occupations based on some consideration ranging from availability to connections but, hardly upon their emotional intelligence or intellect. Though, this was partly due to the social nature of the society, it would be better if students would prepare and engage in occupations that they are comfortable with and that they would excel in. Thus, the ability of emotional intelligence in predicting other outcomes and behaviour in the workplace is calling for further examination. Consequently, the schools are in need to know what really creates job involvement.

In this regard, the researcher noticed that students are prepared and engaged in occupations that are kind of 'readily available' without careful consideration of their God-given intellectual and emotional capabilities. Furthermore, it has been common among parents, guardians and elders to choose occupation for their children and this may be a risk to both students and society. In line with this, the researcher hoped that the information, data and result of this research will enable parents, guardians and teachers to realize the importance of allowing the students to choose careers that commensurate with their emotional intelligence. This will in turn, minimize the problems of job dissatisfaction, unproductivity and failure-imposed career. This study is going to investigate the relationship between emotional intelligence and motivation for occupational preference among junior secondary school students in Birnin Kebbi education zone. Ipaye in Eze (2018) students do not adequately understand their abilities, interest, values and do not generally relate their personal characteristics to the requirement of their preferred occupation.

The roles of the schools and teachers have changed and qualities of teachers have become a decisive factor in providing the students with necessary skills and offering quality education. According to Jones (2001), "teacher is the most dynamic element when we take education as a system." Teachers play a significant role in teaching the students to learn and think, increasing the quality of education and concluding the changes with accomplishments. Therefore, the notions of emotional intelligence and motivation are critical factors in the profession of teaching which mainly comprises of emotions and sensitivities.

Emotional intelligence and motivation are interrelated concepts, supported by their definitions. The word "emotion" is derived from the Latin word "movere" (to move). Emotion can be assumed to have a persistent tendency to behave (Konrad & Hendl, 2005). The word "motivation" is also derived from the word "movere" and "motum". In psychology, it generally refers to process of movement and tendency of an individual to ascertain objective through intrinsic driving forces and showing intentional behaviour (Bingöl, 1998; O'Connor & Carol, 1995; Tarakçioğlu, Sökmen & Boylu: 2010). Commitment is "the force driving an individual to act towards a certain objective. Accordingly, the words "emotion" and "motivation" are derived from similar origins and they are closely related to the concept of commitment.

The studies on emotional intelligence in 1990s were popular and effective (Mayer, Salovey & Caruso, 2000). The studies carried out to find out why individuals with high intelligence levels have always been the best in their business and private lives, (Cooper & Sawaf, 2003) revealed that intelligence on its own was not sufficient for an individual to have achievements in family, education and business life (Maree & Eiselen, 2009). The studies ,carried out so far, have generally examined the relationship between emotional intelligence and leadership, problem solving, decision-making, exhaustion, job satisfaction, creativity and academic achievement. Studies include topics like emotional intelligence of teachers (Walker, 2001; Nelson, Low & Nelson,2005); Penrose, Perry & Ball, 2007); Kafetsios & Zampetakis, 2008); Özmen, 2009), emotional intelligence and motivation (Akpola & Işık, 2012), emotional intelligence and organizational commitment (Nikolau & Tsaousis, 2002); Wong & Law; 2002); Gardner, 2005); Akın, 2010); Güleriyüz, Güney, Aydın & Aşan, (2008); Doğan, (2009); Hosseinzadeh, Yousefzadeh & Mashaikhi (2012).

Motivation is another concept that is emphasized in the profession of teaching and in emotional intelligence. Motivation can be defined as the driving force which is used by individuals to reach some goals or to meet some expectations and requirements (Mullins, 2006), and it has an important role in terms of personal performance and organizational performance (Vural & Coşkun, 2007).

Therefore, several studies can be found in the literature on the relationship between motivation and job satisfaction, performance, communication and personal management. There are studies that examine the relationship between emotional intelligence and motivation on various variables (Anderson & Iwanicki, 1984); Kelley, 1999); Moran, Kilpatrick, Abbott, Dallat & McClune,2001); Wadsworth, 2001); Bennel, 2004); Barlı, Bilgili, Çelik & Bayrakçeken, 2005); Hettiarachchi, 2010); Alam & Farid, 2011); Karabenick & Conley, 2011); Schieb & Karabenick, 2011) and underline the importance of intrinsic motivation of teachers Latham, in Thompson, (2012).

School is an agent of socialization occupying a vital position in determining individual's interest in life. Among the factors in school that influences the individual include range of subject taught, habit of the students, the quality and quantity of the teachers, relevant teaching materials, location of the school, etc. Muhammad (2007) in his work cited Douglas, (1994), that students from rural areas are likely to have less educational aspiration and plans than others from urban environments. Abubakar (2005) opined that school offers individual a new range of experiences through its formal and organized curricular and extra-curricular activities, and through formal interaction with peers, teachers and career officers. Factors like personality, work knowledge and advice are important and influential in students' vocational choices.

Objectives of the Study

Youths in Kebbi State are faced with a lot of problems concerning occupational opportunities. Most of our students are relying on civil service which is very hard to get due to over growing of population. Because of this, youths are liabilities, whereas some depend on their parents, relatives, wealthy ones, politicians which lead them to be areas boys and area girls while others become idleness which may force them to lay hands on others possessions. So, for these reasons there is need to guide and counsel our youths since from adolescence stage to be co-opted with the skills to enable them be self-reliance after graduation, even without government job. The specific objectives of the study include;

1. To find out the relationship between emotional intelligence and motivation for occupational preference among Junior Secondary School Students in Kebbi State.
2. To find out the relationship between emotional intelligence and age of students.
3. To find out the relationship between motivation for occupational preference and age of students.
4. To find out the difference between male and female emotional intelligence of students.
5. To find out the relationship between male and female motivation for occupational preference of students.

Research Questions

The following questions were raised to guide the conduct of the study:

1. Is there any relationship between emotional intelligence and motivation for occupational preference among Junior Secondary School Students in Kebbi State?
2. Is there any relationship between emotional intelligence and age of students?
3. Is there any relationship between motivation for occupational preference and age of students?
4. Is there any difference between male and female emotional intelligence of students?
5. Is there any difference between male and female motivation for occupational preference of students?

Null Hypotheses

In line with the research objectives and questions, the following hypotheses were formulated for the conduct of the study:

H0₁: There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and motivation for occupational preference among Junior secondary school students in Birnin Kebbi Education zone.

H0₂: There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and age of students.

H0₃: There is no significant relationship between motivation for occupational preference and age of students.

H0₄: There is no significant difference between male and female emotional intelligence students.

H0₅: There is no significant difference between male and female motivation for occupational preference of students.

Methodology

This research is correlational designed to solicit information from students on relationship between emotional intelligence and motivation for occupational preference in junior secondary schools in Birnin Kebbi Education zone. The target population of this study consisted of all the male and female junior secondary school students (JSS) in Birnin Kebbi education zone. There were 3102 male and 1048 female students respectively. The population of the study was four thousand one hundred and fifty students (4150). While the sample of the study was three hundred and fifty respondents (350) by using Research Advisor's Table (2006). Similarly, the stratified method of sampling was also used to select eight (8) junior secondary schools from Birnin Kebbi education zone, Kebbi state. The justification for the above selection was to make sure that the objectives of this research are achieved. The instruments used for gathering data for this study were two adopted questionnaires. The instrument has three sections; section A dealt with demographic information of the respondents; section B dealt with Emotional intelligence questionnaire (EIQ) while section C dealt with Motivation for Occupational Preference scale (MOPS) The research questions were prepared to solicit information from the respondents. The demographic information of the respondents includes only age, sex and class. The two instruments were: 'Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire (EIQ) Motivation for Occupational Preference Scale (MOPS).

Result

This chapter presented the results of the analysis based on the data obtained from Junior Secondary School Students in Birnin Kebbi Education Zone, Kebbi state, using a total of 350 respondents to the study, Presentation of data was in line with the research questions that were formulated to guide the study. The following statistical procedures were used in answering the research questions; Descriptive and inferential statistic were used to answer all the research questions using (SPSS). Percentage was used to analyze the information of the respondents.

Table 3: Distribution of the Respondents by Gender

	Variable Option	Frequency	Percentage %
Gender	Male	240	68.6%
	Female	110	31.4%

The table above showed the sex distribution of the respondents used in carrying out this study. The table revealed that 31.4% of the Junior Secondary School Students employed in this study are females while 68.6% are males. This implies that male students are greater in number in participation in the survey than the females.

Table 4: Respondents' Distribution by Age

	Variable Option	Frequency	Percentage %
Age	11 – 12 Years	107	30.6%
	13 – 14 Years	111	31.7%
	15 years and above	132	37.7%

The above table describes the distribution of the respondents by age. The table shows that JS1 has the frequency of 107 with percentage 30.6% of the respondents are within the age group 11-12 years and another group of respondents are within the age of 13-14 with frequency of 111 and the percentage of 31.7 while majority of the respondents have the frequency of 132 with percentage of 37.7 are within 15 years and above. This implies that JS1-3 participated in the survey.

4.3 Testing the Null Hypotheses

This part presented inferential statistical analysis of all the null hypotheses formulated to guide the study. The null hypotheses were tested one after another at 0.05 level of significance.

4.3.1 Null Hypotheses1(H₀₁): There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and motivation for occupational preference among Junior Secondary School Students in Birnin Kebbi Education zone.

Table 5: Relationship between emotional intelligence and motivation for occupational preference

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	r-Cal	p-Value	Decision
Emotional Intelligence	350	33.86	17.09	6.19	.001	H ₀ Rejected
Motivation for Occupation	350	23.72	13.89			

Source: Field Work (2023)

α -value= 0.05

From table 3, it can be seen that relationship between emotional intelligence and motivation for occupational preference was positive and significant, Pearson's $r = (348) 6.19$; $p < 0.05$. Thus, the hypothesis is rejected. This indicates that there is significant relationship between emotional intelligence and motivation for occupational preference because the p-value is less than the 0.05 level of significance. This implies that an increase in the variable of emotional intelligence was accompanied with an increase in motivation for occupational preference.

4.3.2 Null Hypotheses2(H₀₂): There is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and age of students.

Table 6: Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Age of Students

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	r-Cal	p-Value	Decision
Emotional Intelligence	166	20.36	14.39	6.91	.003	H ₀ Rejected
Age	184	33.23	18.39			

Source: Field Work (2023)

α -value= 0.05

From table 4, it can be seen that relationship between emotional intelligence and age was positive and significant, Pearson's $r = (348) 6.91$; $P < 0.05$. Thus, the hypothesis is rejected. This indicates that there is significant relationship between emotional intelligence and age because the p-value of 0.003 is less than the α -value 0.05 ($P < 0.003 < \alpha < 0.05$) level of significance. This implies that an increase in the variable of emotional intelligence was accompanied with an increase in age of the students.

4.3.3 Null Hypotheses 3 (H₀₃): There is no significant relationship between motivation for occupational preference and age of students.

Table 7: Relationship between Motivation for Occupational Preference and Age of Students.

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	r-Cal	p-Value	Decision
Motivation for Occupation	166	47.56	9.39	5.82	.002	H ₀ Rejected
Age	184	33.23	18.39			

Source: Field Work (2023)

α -value= 0.05

From table 5, it can be seen that relationship between motivation for occupational preference and age was positive and significant, Pearson's $r = (348) 5.82$; $P < 0.02$. Thus, the hypothesis is rejected. This indicates that there is significant relationship between motivation for occupational preference and age because the p -value of 0.002 is less than the α -value 0.05 ($P-0.002 < \alpha- 0.05$) level of significance. This implies that an increase in the variable of motivation for occupational preference is accompanied with an increase in the age of the students.

4.3.4 Null Hypotheses 4 (H₀₄): There is no significant difference between male and female emotional intelligence of the students.

Table8: Difference between Male and Female Students' Emotional Intelligence

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-Cal	p-Value	Decision
Male	216	47.67	10.470	.216	.829	H ₀ Accepted
Female	132	47.43	9.228			

Source: Field Work (2023)

α -value= 0.05

From table 6, it can be seen that difference between male and female emotional intelligence though positive was not significant, $t = (346) .216$; $p > 0.05$. Thus, the hypothesis is accepted. This indicates that there is no significant difference in the emotional intelligence of the students because the p -valueof.829 is more than the α -value of 0.05level of significance. This implies that there is no significant difference in the emotional intelligence of the two categories of students (both male and female).

4.3.5 Null Hypotheses 5 (H₀₅): There is no significant difference between male and female motivation for occupational preference of the students.

Table9: Difference between Male and Female Students' Motivation for Occupational Preference

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-Cal	p-Value	Decision
Male	216	47.39	8.997	-.408	.683	H ₀ Accepted
Female	132	47.82	10.065			

Source: Field Work (2023)

α -value= 0.05

From table 7, it can be seen that difference between male and female emotional intelligence was negative and non-significant, $t = (346) -.408$; $p > 0.05$. Thus, the hypothesis is accepted. This indicates that there is no significant difference in the motivation for occupational preference of the students because the p -value of -.408 is more than the α -value of 0.05level of significance. This implies that there is no significant difference in the motivation for occupational preference of the two categories of students (both male and female).

Summary of Major Findings

- i) The following are the major finding of this study:
- ii) There was relationship between emotional intelligence and motivation for occupational preference among Junior secondary school students in Birnin Kebbi Education zone, Kebbi state. The indication of significant relationship between emotional intelligence and motivation for occupational preference was positive because the p -value is less than the 0.05 level of significance. It implied that an increase in the variable of emotional intelligence was accompanied with an increase in motivation for occupational preference.
- iii) There was relationship between emotional intelligence and age of students in Junior secondary school in Birnin Kebbi Education zone, Kebbi state, because the p -value of 0.003 is less than the α -value 0.05 ($P-0.003 < \alpha-$

0.05) level of significance. This implies that an increase in the variable of emotional intelligence was accompanied with an increase in age of the students.

Discussion of Findings

The main objectives of this study were to find out whether there is relationship between emotional intelligence and motivation for occupational preference among junior secondary school students of Birnin Kebbi education zone. The instruments used for gathering information were divided into three main sections as: the demographic data of the respondents, emotional intelligence Questionnaire (EIQ) and scale of motivation for occupational preference (MOPS). The findings revealed that all the hypotheses showed that there was significance relationship between emotional intelligence and motivation for occupational preference among Junior Secondary School students as stated below.

The gender distribution of the respondents used in carrying out this study revealed that 31.4% of the Junior Secondary School Students employed in this study were females while 68.6% were males. This implies that male students are grater in number in participation in the survey than the females. While distribution of the respondents by age showed that JS1 has the frequency of 107 with percentage 30.6% of the respondents are within the age group 11-12 years and another group of respondents are within the age of 13-14 with frequency of 111 and the percentage of 31.7 while majority of the respondents have the frequency of 132 with percentage of 37.7 are within 15years and above This implies that both JS1-3 participated in the survey.

CONCLUSION

Through the findings of this study, it was indicated that; there was significant relationship between emotional intelligence and motivation for occupational preference among junior secondary schools in Birnin Kebbi education zone. There was also significant relationship between emotional intelligence and motivation for occupational preference among students by age in Birnin Kebbi Education zone, Kebbi State. But there was no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and motivation for occupational preference among male and female students in Birnin Kebbi Education zone, Kebbi State. This means that some career choices are more suitable based on the gender as it was revealed by the respondents. Also, the findings in the study showed that the career choices based on interest and willing are more influential than to force the students.

Conclusively, after all the research work, techniques and strategies followed in gathering data, use of valid and reliable instruments, collection of information, analyzing the data, discussion of the findings, the final solution was ‘There was significance relationship between emotional intelligence and motivation for occupational preference among junior secondary schools in Birnin Kebbi education zone.’

5.4 Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study carried out on the relationship between emotional intelligence and motivation for occupational preference among junior secondary schools in Birnin Kebbi education zone. The following recommendations were made.

- I. Parents/guardians should take into consideration that their children’s level of emotional intelligence and this should be one of the yardsticks of allowing them choose commensurate careers. This will in turn minimize the problems of job dissatisfaction and unproductivity in organizations.
- II. Vocational guidance and counselling services should be geared towards ensuring that students make intelligence choice for careers at the right age and which should be in line with their intelligence.
- III. Guidance counsellors should also work earnestly towards ensuring students are guided to choose careers at the right age. In this regard, parents should be sensitized in ways to help towards realization of their children’s goals.
- IV. Guidance counsellors, parents and the whole community should make every effort to develop and maintain the emotional intelligence of the male and female students.
- V. Guidance counsellors, parents and the whole community should make every effort to develop and guide the students in making the right choice of careers irrespective of gender.

Suggestions for Further Studies

Based on the findings of this research work, the researcher is suggesting that:

- i) A research could be conducted on “Students’ perceptions of career aspirations in secondary schools”.
- ii) An investigation can be carried out on “Relationship between parental treatment, socio-economic status and career interest of junior secondary school students”.
- iii) Another research work could be developed on the “Relationship between emotional intelligence and career choice among students in tertiary institutions students in the state”.
- iv) Finally, another research could look into “Parental gender effect in choice of careers among secondary school final year students”.

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